

IMPACT OF COVID-19 ON EDUCATION
Ms. Tejaswi Dinesh Prajapati
Lecturer
H. Mutha College of Arts, Commerce & Science, Kalyan (W)
Ms. Pooja Ramesh Raikwar
Industry Delegates
Abstract:

Covid 19 has its effect on all the sectors of the economy including society, education, health, lifestyle, job sector, etc. Education sector of India and World are badly affected by this Pandemic. As we know due to COVID 19 it has resulted a drastic change in education. Education has changed dramatically with distinctive rise of e-learning where in teaching is done on digital platforms. COVID 19 has affected large number of student all over the country. It has severe impact on the lives of Teachers, Students and their families. But Technology has changed scenario in this pandemic COVID 19. It has stressed on Online Education or Learning hereby making it digitalized. One of the greatest impact is on Education Sector of the country. We can say that technology has played very important role in this pandemic situation. This Pandemic has taught us that change is inevitable and needs to be accepted. But on this note, Education didn't stop at all via various initiatives of the Government. E-Learning is a new way of Learning and which made everything to carry out at ease. To overcome this pandemic situations people or students used various Social Media Platform. During this COVID-19, Government has taken various initiatives and measures for the field of education. As a coin has two sides similarly this digital learning or e-learning has positive as well as negative points of its own.

Keywords - *Covid-19, Pandemic, Education, Impact, Government Initiatives, Digital.*

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Introduction:

Covid -19 stand for Corona Virus and the name given by World Health Organization (WHO) on February 11, 2020. It was identified in 2019 in Wuhan, China. This pandemic hit the country hard and many other sectors as well education sector is also been effected and students ,teachers as well as many people related to education sector is being suffered by that and also in this pandemic crisis food security, public health, employment and labour issues, in particular workers' health and safety get effected. Pandemic has impacted approximately 1.5 million schools and 247 millions have suffered. In this Pandemic situation, learning has now become online and virtually. But in this situation Online Learning has played a vital role. It also provides us flexibility of time and place. Online Learning is very cost effective and can be delivered to many people at a time. It has made possible for to one stay at home and acquire knowledge. This lockdown

has given a ray of hope to students and teachers to continue education process via Online medium. Various apps were used like Zoom, Google Meet, Skype, YouTube, etc. for delivering lectures. Technology has made a turning point in education from TEACHER CENTRIC to both TEACHER and STUDENT CENTRIC EDUCATION. E-learning has now become new normal. Because of Covid-19, there was an impact on Board Examination, Competitive Examination and Entrance Examination as well.

Objectives

- 1] To acquaint various measures taken by Government of India.
- 2] To know about the impact of Covid -19 on Education.
- 3] To get response from students regarding Online Education.
- 4] To highlight Positive and Negative Impact of Covid-19

Methodology

The data used to study the paper is based on primary as well as secondary data. The primary data is collected through Questionnaire (Google Forms) from students with 200 samples which is based on convenience sampling method. The data has been collected from Kalyan – Dombivali. As it was a questionnaire there were chances of partiality or personal bias. The Secondary data is collected through various journals, articles, Weblinks, Newspapers Articles, Etc.

Significance of the Study

This paper gives a brief information about Impact Of Covid-19 on Education but from students point of view. It tries to find out problems of difficulties faced by the students due to Online Learning Process. This also tries to know their views on Online Learning.

Measures Or Initiative Es Taken By The Government

Since all over the country there was lockdown, due to which education sector was highly affected and because of which most exams were cancelled or else postponed. Even final assessment were postponed. After which online learning was boosted up by University Grant Commission (UGC). On this point UGC made two different committees to help out with this online learning. One Committee was formed for Examination and Academic Calendar while Other Committee was formed for Students, Teachers and Education. This was done not to give a break to the education sector and divert students. Ministry of Education took many initiatives so as to save the interest of students and teachers by bringing up many facilities like PM eVIDYA, DIKSHA, SWAYAM, MOOCs, E-textbook, etc. which all were useful for the field of Education.

There are free Online platforms which are as follows :-

1. Zoom – It is an easy, mostly used Cloud platform for video and audio conferencing, chats and webinars for 100 participants.
2. Google Meet – Video call app with chats with maximum 250 people.
3. Skype – Video and audio calls with talk chat and collaborative features.
4. Facebook Live – It is used for businesses, influencers or individuals who likes to broadcast demos or

videos with live chat on facebook.

5. YouTube Live – Huge repository of educational videos and learning channels.
6. Uber Conference – Unlimited video and audio calls with talk, chat and collaborative features in it.
7. Teams – It is for chat, meet, call and collaborative features integrated with Microsoft.
8. Google Classroom – It helps classes to connect remotely, communicate and stay organized.
9. Facebook Get Digital – Lessons plan, conservation starters, activities, videos and other resources for students to stay connected.
10. Khan Academy – One of the self directed learning content with free lessons and practice in various subjects like Math, Science, Humanities, etc.
11. National Digital Library – It has wide range of academic content in different formats and is available in different languages which is useful for all learners.
12. e-PG Pathshalas and e- Pathshala – It is useful for Post Graduates but for all disciplines including arts, humanities, fine arts, natural and mathematical sciences. It is Online Learning App by NCERT for Class 1 to 12.
13. Shodhganga – It is a digital platform which has thesis and Dissertations useful for research students for pursuing PhD.
14. SWAYAM Online Course - It is used for schools and higher education. It includes almost all subjects.SWAYAM Prabha is a 32 DTH TV channel just like Swayam.
15. E-textbooks – E-textbooks are digital textbooks is just like a textbooks but printed version of it. It is technology based which can be downloaded or printed or accessed online.
16. DIKSHA - Digital Infrastructure for Knowledge Sharing. It is an e-learning or Online platform for school education. It is freely accessible to anybody and everybody. It has QR CODE.

Positive Impact Of Covid 19 On Education

- Easily accessible to students from other country to attend lectures
- Teachers become techno savvy
- Education enhance to new level from chalkboard to virtual
- Learning materials improve from hard copy to soft copy
- Rise in teaching community and collaborative work

Negative Impact Of Covid 19 On Education

- Difficulty in students admission and assessment process
- Teachers can't pay attention to all students at same time
- Offline teaching not that effective
- Students are not attentive as offline

Data Analysis And Findings

TABLE 1 DEMOGRAPHIC OF RESPONDENTS :-

AGE		GENDER		EDUCATION QUALIFICATION	
5 – 15	9%	FEMALE	47%	SCHOOLING	35%
15 – 25	86%	MALE	53%	UNDERGRADUATE	56.5%
25 AND ABOVE	5%			GRADUATE	09%
				POST GRADUATE	4.5%
				PROFESSIONAL	7.5%

Interpretation :- This table depicts demographic information of the respondents which reveals that majority falls under 15-25 years and maximum are males. Most of the respondents are undergraduates.

DAIGRAM 2 RELATED TO PANDEMIC SITUATION

How Did you go through the Pandemic Situation?
200 responses

Interpretation :- This Pie diagram shows responses on Pandemic situation. 35% of the respondents were under stressful situation whereas 17.5% respondents were not in stressful situation. 23% respondents were certainly stressful.

DIAGRAM 3 :- COMFORT WITH ONLINE EDUCATION

Are you all comfortable with Online Education ?
200 responses

Interpretation:- This Pie Diagram shows that maximum respondents were not comfortable whereas some were little bit comfortable. Only 26% were comfortable.

Devices used for Online Learning
200 responses

DIAGRAM 4 :- DEVICES USED

Interpretation:- This shows that maximum respondents used Mobile Phones and after that few used Laptops and very few of them used PC or Personal Computers.

DIAGRAM 5 :- MEDIUM OR PLATFORM

Medium or Platform used by you for learning
200 responses

Interpretation:- This depicts that Maximum number of respondents used Zoom App and least used was Teams and Skype by None.

DIAGRAM 6 :- ONLINE LEARNING MORE EFFECTIVE THAN OFFLINE

Online Teaching Or Learning is more effective than Offline Teaching Or Learning
200 responses

Interpretation:- This Pie diagram shows that maximum respondents were strongly disagree with Online Learning and very few are in favour of Online Learning.

DAIGRAM 7 :- AWARE WITH GOVERNMENT INITIATIVES

Interpretation:- This shows that maximum respondents were aware with Government Initiatives and few were not aware of this initiatives.

DIAGRAM 8 :- SOCIAL MEDIA PLATFORM USED FOR RELAXATION IN PANDEMIC

Most preferred Social media platforms during Pandemic for relaxation
200 responses

Interpretation:- This depicts that YouTube was most preferred while Linked In was the least preferred. People have also used Whatsapp , Instagram and Snapchat too.

Are you able to cope up with this learning Or teaching process?
200 responses

DAIGRAM 9 :- COPE UP WITH LEARNING

Interpretation:- This show that there is a mixed sort of response where maximum were able to cope up and few were not able to cope up with this online learning.

DAIGRAM 10 :- HOURS SPEND

How many hours did you spend on Online Learning?
200 responses

Interpretation:- This shows that Mostly respondent have spent 2 to 3 hours and very few spent more than 5 hours

DIAGRAM 11 :- NETWORK DIIFICULTIES

Did you face any network issues or difficulties in Online Education Process?
200 responses

Interpretation:- This shows that most of them faced difficulties in this online learning method.

DIAGRAM 12 :- EFFECT ON STUDY PLAN

Did you change your study plan due to COVID-19 ?
200 responses

Interpretation:- This shows that many of the respondents have changed their study pan whereas some of them didn't change at all. It is also seen that 20% were neutral.

DIAGRAM 13 :- HEARD ABOUT GOVERNMENT INITIATIVES

Are you all aware with Government Initiatives Or Measures?

200 responses

Following are the Government Initiatives have you heard Or know about it.

200 responses

Interpretation :- This shows that most of the respondents are aware about E-Textbooks and DIKSHA app. Respondents are also aware about other Government Initiatives as well.

Conclusion

COVID-19 has impact on Education sector. It had challenges as well as opportunities. This Pandemic has taught that change is to be accepted and made us Techno Savy. It is really difficult to predict that how long will it take to get everything normal but till then we have to make E-Learning as New Normal. There is no doubt that Online Education is ineffective but we can never change our Traditional Method of Teaching. Even Government has taken measures during this lockdown by upgrading Online Learning and in some areas which are remote areas where there is no access

to Internet facilities there Television and Radio acted the main source for imparting education to the students. In this, as per the findings some were comfortable with Online Learning but few were not comfortable. Even for Online Learning they need devices and proper Internet facilities without which they had to suffer. People were also aware with Government Initiatives and they have even tried few of them. In this Pandemic situation we learned about co-operation with each other. As this was toughest time for all of us but we will try to overcome it and evolved themselves through various Social Media Platforms. In our finding we learnt that students had to face lot of problems.

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